

its N¹-atom linked to a thiazole nucleus at position-2 has been reported. 2-(3'-Methylpyrazol-5-one-1'-yl)-4-arylthiazoles (**1**) were synthesised from the reaction of 3-methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one with α -haloketones. 3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one was obtained by cyclisation of thiosemicarbazone of ethylacetoacetate in ammoniacal methanol.

1a, R=H
1b, R=Cl
1c, R=Br

The structural assignments of **1a-c** were based on their element analysis and spectral data. Though the ir spectra did not display any carbonyl band, a broad band at 3400 cm^{-1} (enolic OH) was noted, whilst the pmr spectra in addition to a broad multiplets at $\delta 7.2-8.2$ (aromatic, thiazole ring proton and pyrazole-4 proton) revealed a singlet of one-proton intensity at $\delta 5.2$ attributable to the enolic hydroxyl proton and also a singlet of three-proton intensity at $\delta 2.2$ ascribed to the methyl proton at position-3. Absence of methylene signal support the enolic structure. The enolic structure strongly supported by mass spectra was due to an initial fragmentation of pyrazolone ring with sequential expulsion of N₂ and CO thereby resulted in the formation of an intense ion at m/z 41. However, Desmarchelier and Johns⁴ observed that the initial loss of .N₂H or .N₂R followed by a rapid loss of CO was a cause of major fragmentation in case of pyrazolone having enolic structure. These compounds (**1a-c**) are under active screening for pharmacological activities.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected.

3-Methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one: Thiosemicarbazone of ethylacetoacetate (5 g) was dissolved in ammoniacal methanol (1 ml of ammonia in 9 ml of methanol) and allowed to stand for 0.5 h. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 180° (lit.⁴ 180°).

2-(3'-Methylpyrazol-5-one-1'-yl)-4-phenylthiazole (1a): A mixture of 3-methyl-1-thiocarbamylpyrazol-5-one (1.57 g, 0.01 mol) and phenacyl bromide (1.99 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed

for 2 h. The resulting solid was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide, filtered, washed and crystallised from acetic acid to yield colourless crystals (**1a**; 61%), m.p. 191° (Found: C, 60.5; H, 4.0; N, 16.2; S, 12.3. C₁₃H₁₁ON₂S requires: C, 60.7; H, 4.3; N, 16.3; S, 12.5%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3400, 3040, 1610, 1540, 1510, 1480, 1410, 980 and 700 cm^{-1} ; δ (TMS; CDCl₃+DMSO-d₆) 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.22 (1H, s, OH) and 7.2-8.2 (7H, m, ArH, thiazole and pyrazole-4 protons); M^+ : 258 (100%), 160 (4%), 134 (10%), 102 (11%), 69 (4%) and 41 (4.3%); **1b** (60%), m.p. 208° ; **1c** (51%), m.p. 193° .

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Synthesis and Characterisation of Salicylic Acid-Dithiobiuret-Trioxane Resin†

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In recent years, considerable attention has been focussed on the synthesis and the study of organic polymers which behave like amorphous semi-conductors. In this communication, we report the synthesis and characterisation of salicylic acid-dithiobiuret-trioxane (SDT) resins.

Experimental

The SDT resins were prepared by condensing salicylic acid (S) and dithiobiuret (D) with trioxane (T) in the mole ratio of 1 : 1 : 2, 2 : 1 : 3 and 3 : 1 : 4, respectively, in presence of 2 M HCl. The mixture was heated at $130 \pm 2^\circ$ in an oil-bath for 4 h¹. The resulting polymeric resin was washed with hot water and then with ether to remove the unreacted monomers. It was purified by dissolving in 8%

† Part of the paper presented at the 23rd. Annual Convention of Chemists, Annamalainagar, 1986.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL AND INTRINSIC VISCOSITY DATA OF RESINS

Resin	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Mol. formula	Mol. wt. of single unit	η dl/g ⁻¹
	C	H	N	S			
SDT (1 : 1 : 2)	44.21 (44.44)	3.74 (3.69)	14.00 (14.14)	21.05 (21.55)	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	297	0.068
SDT (2 : 1 : 3)	50.96 (51.00)	3.72 (3.8)	9.30 (9.39)	14.14 (14.31)	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	447	0.046
SDT (3 : 1 : 4)	55.18 (55.08)	3.98 (3.93)	6.78 (6.88)	10.18 (10.49)	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	610	0.040

NaOH and precipitated by adding 1 : 1 (v/v) concentrated HCl-water, then washed with hot water, dried and kept in vacuum over silica gel.

Composition of all the SDT resins were determined for C, H, N and S. The number average molecular weights were estimated by conductometric titrations in non-aqueous medium. The intrinsic viscosity was measured in DMF at 30° using a Tuan-Fuoss viscometer. Ir spectra were recorded on a Specord IR-75 spectrophotometer, and reflectance and absorption spectra on a Varian DMS-80 UV-VIS double beam spectrophotometer. Electrical conductivity measurements were carried out on a BPL (India) Million megohmmeter. TGA was performed on a Perkin-Elmer thermal analyser. XRD were recorded on a Phillips PW-1700 diffractometer.

Results and Discussion

All the SDT resins are white in colour and soluble in DMF, and aqueous sodium and potassium hydroxides. The melting points are in the range 130–200°. The elemental analysis data are given in Table 1. Conductometric titrations were carried out in DMF against standard alcoholic KOH and also against standard tetra-n-butylammonium hydroxide in DMF. From the plots of specific conductance against milliequivalents of titrant base added, the first break and the last break are noted (Table 2). The degree of polymerisation ($\overline{DP}$) are

TABLE 2—MOLECULAR WEIGHT DATA BY CONDUCTOMETRIC TITRATION

Resin	First stage of neutralisation (meq/100 g resin)	Final stage of neutralisation (meq/100 g resin)	Degree of polymerisation DP	$\overline{M}_n$
SDT (1 : 1 : 2)	92 ^a (714) ^b	1 380 (10 710)	15	4 455
SDT (2 : 1 : 3)	92 (714)	1 564 (12 138)	17	7 600
SDT (3 : 1 : 4)	92 (714)	1 380 (10 710)	15	9 150

^aValues for alcoholic KOH used as titrant base; ^bValues for tetra-n-butylammonium hydroxide used as titrant base.

obtained from the ratio of total milliequivalents of base for neutralisation of all COOH groups to the milliequivalents for neutralisation of first COOH

group (first break). The value of (DP) was multiplied by the average molecular weight of the repeating unit to give the number average molecular weight (Table 2) The $\overline{M}_n$ values thus obtained for both the titrant bases used are comparable within limits of experimental error.

The viscosity of the SDT resins was measured in DMF at six different concentrations at 30°. The value of intrinsic viscosity (η), determined by using the Huggin and Krammer relations,

$$\eta_{sp}/C = \eta + K_1(\eta)^2 C \tag{1}$$

$${}^1_n \eta_{rel}/C = \eta - K_2(\eta)^2 C \tag{2}$$

was found to be in good agreement (Table 1)¹⁻³.

From the ir spectral studies it is found that all the resins give rise to similar spectra. A broad band containing several inflections appearing at 2 300–3 400 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the stretching vibration of phenolic OH group and acid group. A medium band at nearly 2 600 cm⁻¹ is attributable to hydrogen bonded phenolic OH group. The bands in the regions 2 800–3 300, 1 400–1 500, 1 150–1 350 and 750–800 cm⁻¹ suggest the presence of methylene bridges in the STD resins⁴. A sharp peak at 1 600 cm⁻¹ may be ascribed to aromatic skeletal ring breathing modes. The band at about 1 650 cm⁻¹ may be due to the stretching vibration of C=O of salicylic acid group. A band at about 860 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to C=S stretch. The band at 1 050–1 100 cm⁻¹ also indicates the presence of C=S⁴. A strong absorption at 2 800–3 300 cm⁻¹ is assignable to NH group. However, a broad band around 3 050 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to NH of dithiobiuret unit.

To evaluate the thermal stability and ascertain the characteristic parameters, TGA measurements have been carried out (Table 3). Weight-loss in all the resins starts after about 200° and occurs in three stages. The initial and final decomposition temperature ranges are summarised in Table 3. The initial mass loss may be due to solvent or moisture entrapped in the resin. The Sharp-Wentworth method was applied to the TG data to determine the energy of activation and the order of reaction. The comparative values of onset decomposition temperatures show the highest value for SDT (3 : 1 : 4). The stability is found to be of the order, SDT (3 : 1 : 4) > SDT (2 : 1 : 3) > SDT (1 : 1 : 2).

TABLE 3—THERMOGRAVIMETRIC DATA OF RESINS

Resin	Weight-loss at temp. (°C), %						Onset decomp. temp. °C	Energy of activation (kcal/mol ⁻¹)		Order of reaction (n)
	100°	200°	300°	400°	500°	550°		ΔE_1^{**}	ΔE_2^{**}	
SDT (1 : 1 : 2)	2.5	5.0	33.4	39.5	43.0	46.3	227.28	18.98	0.915	1
SDT (2 : 1 : 3)	1.0	5.5	40.0	43.0	47.5	51.0	224.88	24.64	0.915	1
SDT (3 : 1 : 4)	2.8	4.7	34.5	38.15	43.8	48.0	236.11	28.97	1.600	1

*225–300°C. **300–550°C.

The study of reflectance spectra in solid phase showed that the maximum absorption is at 290 nm for all the SDT resins. The spectra is due to charge transfer transition. The absorption spectra in DMF of all the SDT resins show two bands at 305 and 318 nm. This indicates that the resin containing thionyl groups having double bonds separated by two or more single bonds exhibits the bands due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in the range 300–350 nm⁸. Thus the reflectance spectra also gave nearly the same band as were obtained in their electronic spectra in solution indicating thereby no dissociation of the resin in solution. The slight shifting of the band observed in the absorption spectra may be due to solvent effect.

The resins have been characterised with respect to its semiconducting properties. To study the semiconducting nature, DC resistivity was measured in the temperature range 300–400 K. Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity predicts that all the resins are semiconducting in nature⁶⁻¹⁰ (Fig. 1).

From the X-ray diffraction pattern it is observed that the resins have broad band (halo) characterised by maximum intensity at particular d -values. The lattice dimensions show that all the polymeric resins are amorphous in nature¹¹⁻¹³. The interatomic distance R , calculated by the formula $R = 5\lambda/8 \sin \theta'$ responsible for a strong maxima in the diffraction pattern at angle θ , is equal to 1.25 times the d spacing, calculated with the aid of Bragg equation, $2d \sin \theta = n\lambda$. Table 4 shows the variations in the d spacing.

The SDT resins in the present study are terpolymer and hence it is very difficult to assign their exact structures. Considering the linear structure of salicylic acid–trioxane polymer and linear branched structure of dithiobiuret–trioxane polymer, the most probable structure of SDT resins may be a linear or a sparse branched linear structure (1).

According to conductometric titration method, it has been observed that the ratio of salicylic acid and dithiobiuret is approximately equal to 1 : 1 (Table 1) for those polymers which have been prepared from their equimolar proportions. Hence

Fig. 1. Plots of conductivity vs temperature of resins: (A) SDT 1 : 1 : 2 ($\Delta E = 0.41$ eV), (B) SDT 2 : 1 : 3 (0.55) and (C) SDT 3 : 1 : 4 (0.60).

TABLE 4—POSITION OF MOST INTENSE PEAK IN AMORPHOUS PATTERN OF RESINS

Resin	$d = \frac{\lambda}{2 \sin \theta}$ Å	$R = \frac{5 \lambda}{8 \sin \theta}$ Å
SDT (1 : 1 : 2)	2.81	3.52
SDT (2 : 1 : 3)	4.14	5.18
SDT (3 : 1 : 4)	2.81	3.52

an average molecular weight of repeating unit present in the SDT (1 : 1 : 2) resin may be taken as

297 g mol⁻¹ by considering the average repeating unit as structure 1.

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Coumarins from *Eupatorium ayapana*

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EUPATORIUM ayapana Linn. (Compositae), an aromatic undershrub, is a native of America now naturalised in many parts of India. The plant is known for its various medicinal uses¹. Earlier reports described the isolation of ayapin² and

7-methoxycoumarin³ (herniarin) from this plant. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of five additional coumarins from this plant.

The combined petroleum ether and chloroform extracts of milled whole plants (1.5 kg) after the usual work up followed by column chromatography and preparative tlc led to the isolation of five compounds of which three designated as compounds A, B and C were new isolates besides ayapin and herniarin. Similarly, the alcoholic extract yielded two compounds designated as compounds D and E.

Compound-A (20 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 117–18°, C₁₁H₁₀O₄, M⁺ 206; ν_{max} (KBr) 1 720 (α,β-unsaturated lactone) and 1 400–1 600 (Ar); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) 209 (4.58), 255 (3.88) and 316 (4.36); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.25 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-3), 7.05 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-5), 7.42 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-6) and 8.05 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4). The above data were found to be consistent with that reported for daphnetin dimethyl ether⁴.

Compound-B (18 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 185–86°, C₁₀H₈O₄, M⁺ 192; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 720 (α,β-unsaturated lactone) and 1 400–1 600 (Ar); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) 207 (4.52), 260 (3.99) and 317 (4.15); λ_{max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ε) 279 (4.27) and 327 (4.03) indicative of a phenolic OH group; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.28 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 7.1 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-5), 7.3 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-6) and 7.9 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4). On the basis of the above data compound-B was identified as hydrangetin⁵.

Compound-C (17 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 169–70°, C₁₀H₈O₄, M⁺ 192; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 720 (α,β-unsaturated lactone) and 1 400–1 600 (Ar); ν_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) 207 (4.84), 257 (3.95) and 322 (4.36); λ_{max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ε) 274 (3.9) and 376 (4.45) indicative of a phenolic OH group; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.22 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 6.87 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5), 7.38 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-6) and 7.93 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-4). It was characterised as daphnetin-7-methyl ether⁶.

Compound-D (17 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 225–26°, C₉H₆O₃, M⁺ 162; ν_{max} 3 400 (OH) and 1 725 (α,β-unsaturated lactone); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) 204 (4.33) and 324 (4.10); λ_{max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ε) 229 (3.94) and 370 (4.25) indicative of phenolic OH moiety; δ (CD₂COCD₂) 6.1 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 7.74 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-4) and 6.8–7.4 (3H, m, ArH). It was identified as umbelliferone⁶.

Compound-E (22 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 255–56°, C₉H₆O₄, M⁺ 190; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH) and 1 725 (α,β-unsaturated lactone); λ_{max} (MeOH) (log ε) 209 (4.51), 262 (3.88) and 327 (4.10); λ_{max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ε) 211 (4.51), 279 (4.06) and 379 (4.03) indicative of phenolic OH group; λ_{max} (MeOH+AlCl₃) (log ε)